

As Study on Consumer Preference on Telemarketing in Tirunelveli City

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Abstract

Telemarketing has added a new medium to the marketing tricks. The article briefly discusses the benefits and limitations of telemarketing as part of an overall marketing campaign. Tele marketing is a marketing strategy that involves connecting with customers over the telephone or, more recently, through web-based. Any organization interested in using telemarketing must have a strong understanding of the products it wishes to market. Telemarketing is a service level and advertising strategy customer which helps in achieving the aimed position in the market. Through the telemarketing is a popular strategy in modern days people are moving towards the new techniques, so the paper has discussed the consumer preference on telemarketing strategy. The researcher has used 50 respondent as their sample for the study.

Keyword: Telemarketing, telesales, leads generation, and relationship management.

Introduction

Telemarketing is a direct marketing method, which is concerned with selling products and services to prospective customers via the telephone. The person engaged in such an activity called a sales person. The use of telemarketing was popularized in the 1970 and since then it has become a staple of multi-layered marketing plans. Telemarketing consists of lead generation, which involves research on a perspective, customer sales and outbound calling. Telemarketing can also include recorded sales pitches programmed to be played over the phone via automatic dealing. Telemarketing is defined as contacting, qualifying and canvassing prospective customers using telecommunication devices such as telephone, fax and internet. The two major categories of telemarketing are business-to-business and business-to-consumer. The former is concerned with transacting goods and services between businesses, whereas the latter focuses on serving products and services to the end consumer. The person at the other end of the phone is a telemarketer. When an organization or company is in search of analysis for growth, telemarketing is often a top consideration.

Objectives

- To study the market institution, programs and opportunities.
- To analyze and generate leads for future recruitment.
- To collect data to understand market trends.

Scope

Telemarketing is the process of using the telephone to generate leads, make sales, or gather marketing information. Telemarketing consists of handing incoming telephone calls-often generated by broad cast advertising, direct mail, or catalogues and taking orders for a wide range of product.

Analyses

Table 1 Shows the Demographic Profile of the Respondents

S.No	Categories	No.respondent	Percentage
Age			
1	Less than 30	30	60
2	Above 30	20	40
	Total	50	100
Gender			
1	Male	35	70
2	Female	15	30
	Total	50	100
Income			
1	Below 50k	26	52
2	Above 50k	24	48
	Total	50	100
Marital Status			
1	Married	27	54
2	Unmarried	23	46
	Total	50	100
Education			
1	Literate	23	46
2	Illiterate	27	54
	Total	50	100
Geographical			
1	Urban	24	48
2	Rural	26	52
	Total	50	100

The above table shows that 60% of the respondent belongs to the age of less than 30 40% of the respondents are to the age group of above 30. 70% Of the respondents are male and 30% of the respondent is female 54% of the respondents are married and 46% of the respondent are unmarried 46% of the respondent are literate and 54% of the respondents are illiterate 48% of the respondents are from urban area and 52% of the respondents are from rural area.

Table 2 Usage of Mass Media

S.No	Mass Media	No of Respondent	Percentage
1	News paper	20	40
2	Watching television	10	20
3	Listening	9	18
4	Internet	11	22
	Total	50	100

The above table shows 40% respondent belongs to the news paper 20% respondent are watching television, 18% respondent belongs to listening, 22% of respondents are using the internet.

Tables 3 Time Spend for Telemarketing

S.No	Use in Time Spend	No of Respondent	Percentage
1	1 hour	10	20
2	2 hours	15	30
3	3 hours	10	20
4	5 hours	9	18
5	5 > hours	6	12
	Total	50	100

The above table shows 20% respondent are using 1 hour, 30% respondent is using 2 hours, 20% respondent is spending for 3 hours in the telemarketing 18% respondent use telemarketing for 5 hours and 12% of the respondents are spending the time more than 5 hours in telemarketing.

Tables 4 More People Feel About Advertisement

S.No	Feel about Advertisement	No of Respondent	Percentage
1	Informative	11	22
2	Feel like buying it	12	24
3	Waste of time	14	28
4	Just a marketing gimmick	10	20
5	Cannot fully trust the ads	3	6
	Total	50	100

The above table shows 22% of the respondent are feel informative about advertng, 24% of the respondents feel like buying 28% respondent of the advertising the waste of time 20% respondent of the just a marketing gimmick 6% respondent the fully trust the ads to the advertisement.

Tables 5 Factors Consider to be Purchasing Durable Products

S.No	Factors	No of Respondent	Percentage
1	Its price is important	10	20
2	No compromise for quality	12	24
3	Utility is important	14	28
4	It looks attractive	9	18
5	It is a symbol of status	5	10
	Total	50	100

The above table shows 20% of the respondents of the price is an important, 24% respondent have no compromise for the quality of the product, 28% respondent the purchasing utility of products, 18% respondents looks and attractive of a product, 5% respondent of the purchase of durable products.

Tables 6 Most People Doing for Teleshopping

S.No	Teleshopping Usages	No of Respondent	Percentage
1	Convenient	12	24
2	Economic	13	26
3	Luxury	10	20
4	Unique experience	5	10
5	A symbol of status	10	20
	Total	50	100

The above table shows 24% of convenient the teleshopping 26% respondent of the economic 20% respondent the luxury teleshopping 20% respondent of the unique experience 20% respondent the teleshopping usages

Tables 7 Order of the Place

S.No	Place	No of Respondent	Percentage
1	Online	13	26
2	Telephone	12	24
3	Distributors	15	30
4	Another mode 10	20	10
	Total	50	100

The above table shows 26% respondent of the online shopping, 24% respondent the telephone, 15% respondent are distributors order of the place 10% respondent the other mode of the place.

Tables 8 Influence the Purchase Decision

S.No	Decision for Purchase	No of Respondent	Percentage
1	Family	15	30
2	Friends	10	20
3	Working area	12	24
4	Others	13	26
	Total	50	100

The above table shows 30% respondent of the family purchase decision 20% respondent are friends purchase 24% respondent of the working area 26% respondent is the other influence the purchase decisions.

Findings

The finding of the present revealed the following.

- The majority of the respondents are male with 70%.
- The majority of the respondents are married with 54 %.
- The majority of the respondents are education with illiterate 54%.
- The majority of the respondents are geographical with rural 52%.

- The majority of the respondents are newspapers at 40%.
- The majority of the respondents are newspapers at 40%.
- 30% respondent is using 2 hours.
- 28% respondent of the advertising the waste of time.
- 28% respondent the purchasing utility of products.
- 26% respondent of the economic.
- 26% respondent of the online shopping.
- 26% respondent is the other influence the purchase decisions.
- The majority of the respondent's income lay down below 50K with 52%.

Suggestion

- The above modern techniques lead to increasing the level of cost-effective achievement of the concern.
- It yields time-saving. Attracting the customer in the shorter period.
- Even though it gives the profitability to the firms, the advertisement must have some social responsibilities. So it must be the favor to both firms as well as customer, then only it gives much effective.
- Telemarketing consists of lead generation, which involves research on a perspective, customer sales and outbound calling.

Conclusion

Telemarketing is the cost-effective marketing tool that helps your business in expanding business sales. There are a great number of business to business telemarketing companies are available that offers quality services at the cost-effective price range you should always choose a reliable telemarketing company so that you can reap the major benefits.

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